

×*Echinabeckia*, a New Nothogenus for Hybrids Between *Echinacea* Moench and *Rudbeckia* L. (Asteraceae)

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Abstract—The nothogeneric name ×*Echinabeckia* for hybrids between *Echinacea* Moench and *Rudbeckia* L. (Asteraceae) is proposed.

In 2014, Dutch plant breeder Eternal Plant Boijl B.V. released a purported *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench × *Rudbeckia hirta* L. hybrid under the now trademarked name ECHIBECKIA®.² No nothogeneric name has so far been published for hybrids between *Echinacea* Moench and *Rudbeckia* L. Since it seems undesirable to use a registered trademark as a taxon name, a slightly different name is proposed here:

×*Echinabeckia* M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.**

Echinacea Moench × *Rudbeckia* L.

×*Echinabeckia* 'ET-RDB 01'
('ECHIBECKIA®
SUMMERINA® ORANGE')

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² Echibeckia 014956262. European Union Intellectual Property Office.
<https://euipo.europa.eu/eSearch/#details/trademarks/014956262> (accessed 3 September 2019)